

Ratooning of paddy

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A number of cultures and varieties proposed for introduction in Tamil Nadu were observed at Aduthurai during 1976 to ascertain adaptability. Each entry was sown in a 5-sqm plot at a seeding rate of 10 g/sq m. Seedlings from a third of the plot were pulled and planted *in situ* on the 25th day, those from another third on the 40th day, and those from the remaining third were allowed to grow

undisturbed as a broadcast crop. NPK was applied at 50–50–50g/ha on the 25th day after sowing, and nitrogen at 25 kg/ha on the 40th and 60th days.

The main crop was cut at 15 cm from ground level. The ratoon crop was not fertilized and was harvested at 55 to 60 days. Ratooning ability was calculated by yield instead of by the IRRRI method based on number of tillers.

Two short- and 11 medium-duration varieties yielded more than 5 t/ha as main crop, and 2.5 t/ha and above as ratoon crop in all three methods of cultivation (see table).

RP 1045-5-6-2, IET 2885, GMR 13, and IR1529-680-3 ratooned well after

any main-crop treatment. ADT 30 as main crop yielded less than 5 t/ha but had more than 90% ratooning potential.

Between cultivation methods of the main crop for the purpose of ratooning, transplanting at 25 days was superior to both broadcasting and transplanting at 40 days. The latter was on par with broadcasting.

The total yields of main and ratoon crops were:

	Yield (t/ha)
Broadcast	9.6 a
Transplanted at 25 days	11.1 ab
Transplanted at 40 days	9.9 b
L.S.D. (P=0.05)	1.2

Grain yield (t/ha) of main and ratoon crops. Tamil Nadu, India.

Variety	Parents	Grain yield (t/ha) at given cultivation method					
		Broadcast		Transplanted		On 40th day	
		Main crop	Ratoon crop	On 25th day	Main crop	Ratoon crop	Main crop
<i>85–115 days</i>							
ADT 30	IR262/ADT 27	4.1	3.9	4.3	4.4	2.4	3.4
ADT 31	IR8/Cult. 340	5.5	2.9	7.9	2.8	4.6	2.4
CR 146-224	CR 10-114/CR 115	7.6	^a	10.2	3.3	5.4	2.8
<i>120–135 days</i>							
RP 1045-5-6-2	RP 31-49-2/LZN	10.6	4.4	9.4	4.8	9.5	4.7
RP 1045-10-6-2-1		6.1	3.3	6.1	3.1	5.3	4.0
IET 2885 (RPW 6-1 3)	IR8/Siam 29	6.4	3.0	11.2	4.0	9.2	3.3
GMR 13 (RP 9-6)	IR8/W 1251	6.2	5.2	1.7	4.5	6.4	5.2
IR1529-680-3	IR24/Sigadis ² /TN1	8.5	3.2	6.9	3.4	6.0	3.6
IR20	IR262/TKM 6	6.0	2.1	5.5	2.1	7.5	2.9
CR 1001	CR 70/Pankaj	6.8	2.1	1.6	3.5	5.9	3.3
CR 1003	”	5.3	2.5	6.3	4.5	5.1	4.5
Ponni	Tg. 65/Mayang Ebos -8)	^b	2.3	6.9	4.0	5.9	3.6
AD 54-1 (BB)	Bhavani/Ponni	5.1	1.1	1.0	3.1	5.9	3.9
AD 2114	IARI 6609/Peta	8.0	^a	5.2	3.3	6.3	3.4

^aDamaged by rats. ^bAffected by pests and diseases.

Rice-based cropping systems

Effect of tillage method and rice stubble on bean fly *Ophomyia phaseoli* infesting cowpea planted after lowland rice

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Rice followed by cowpeas and rice

followed by mung beans are common cropping patterns in low land rainfed areas of the Philippines. Farmers normally do not till the soil for the second crop, but broadcast legume seeds directly into standing rice stubble.

The Philippine cropping systems program is testing the performance of improved varieties of grain legumes under several tillage practices. We sampled the

insect populations in EG2 cowpeas in fields where four methods had been used to establish the crop after rice: 1) plowing and harrowing twice; 2) plowing furrows between alternate rows of rice with rice stubble cut to ground level; 3) plowing furrows between alternate rows of rice with uncut stubble; and 4) no tillage with seeds dibbled in rows at the base of rice hills with rice stubble uncut. Half of the

Effect of tillage method, height of rice stubble, and insecticide on bean fly population infesting cowpeas planted after lowland rice. IRRI, 1977.

Tillage	Rice stubble	Bean fly counts ^a						
		Adults (no./18-m row)			Larvae + pupae (no./25 plants)		Infested plants (%)	
		5 DE	10 DE	15 DE	21 DE		21 DE	
Untreated plots			Treated plots ^b	Untreated plots	Treated plots	Untreated plots		
Plowed and harrowed twice	Plowed under	15 a	12 a	1 a	10 ab	19 a	52 bc	88 a
Furrows plowed between rice rows	Cut to 1 cm	8 a	2 a	1 a	5 bc	9 abc	37 cd	62 b
Furrows plowed between rice rows	30-40 cm ^c	1 b	2 b	1 a	5 bc	6 bc	30 de	29 de
No tillage; seed dibbled in rows	30-40 cm ^c	0 b	2 b	2 b	3c	3 c	17 e	20 de

^aWithin counting dates means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. DE = days after crop emergence.

^b0.25 kg cyanophenphos (Surecide 25 EC) a.i./ha sprayed at 5 and 15 DE.

^cRatoon crop.

plots received insecticide sprays (Surecide 25 EC) at 5 and 15 days after emergence at the rate of 0.25 kg a.i./ha. The trial was replicated three times.

The population of the bean fly *Ophiomyia phaseoli* was low in plots with standing rice stubble and where the rice had ratooned (see table). In the early growth stages of cowpeas, the rice stubble evidently interfered with the host-seeking responses of the bean fly. At 5 days after cowpea emergence (DE), significantly fewer adults were observed ovipositing

in cowpeas among the 30- to 40-cm rice stubble. At 10 DE bean fly oviposition was restricted to the rice that had ratooned in the treatment where stubble was cut to ground level.

As forms of cultural control, rice stubble and ratoon rice were as effective as insecticide protection in preventing bean fly buildup at the crucial early stages of cowpea growth. At 21 DE no significant difference was observed between plots that had been treated with insecticide and those that had not been

in terms of the number of larvae and pupae per 25 plants and the percentage of infested plants in 30-40 cm stubble. The bean fly population was high in the untreated plots that received the high tillage treatment (19 larvae + pupae/25 plants and 88% infested plants). Infestation levels were intermediate in the plots where stubble was cut (9 larvae + pupae/25 plants and 62% infested plants). ~~W~~

Promising varieties of rainfed legumes grown at zero tillage after paddy rice

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The inclusion of upland crops such as legumes increases overall crop productivity in rice-based cropping systems. Legumes, particularly soybeans, mung beans, and cowpeas, augment the nutritional output of cropping patterns. To ensure the success of subsequent cropping patterns, scientists must first identify high yielding varieties of suitable legumes.

Ten promising varieties each of soybeans, mung beans, and cowpeas were evaluated at zero tillage under rainfed conditions after a crop of paddy rice at IRRI in mid-December 1976. The legumes were planted immediately after rice harvest to capitalize on the

Origin and agronomic data of promising varieties of soybeans, mung beans, and cowpeas planted after paddy rice at zero tillage under rainfed conditions. IRRI, 1976-77 dry season.

Crop, variety	Origin	Seed yield (t/ha)	Yield advantage over check (%)	Maturity (days)	Ht (cm)
<i>Soybeans</i>					
Kuro daizu	Japan	1.77	88	19	59
Bethel	USA	1.25	33	81	40
UPLB-SY 2	Philippines	1.22	30	76	49
Multivar 80	USA	1.21	29	77	43
TK 5 (check)	Taiwan	0.94	-	80	36
<i>Mung beans</i>					
CES 1D-21	Philippines	1.43	25	78	61
EG Glabrous # 3	Philippines	1.35	18	73	69
CES 55	Philippines	1.24	9	72	78
Dau Mo	Vietnam	1.22	7	73	69
CES 87 (check)	Philippines	1.14	-	71	18
<i>Cowpeas</i>					
EG #3	Philippines	1.47	30	75	51
EG #2	Philippines	1.44	27	74	49
TVU 4-b-b-10-b	IITA ^a , Nigeria	1.29	14	75	65
All season	USA	1.18	4	75	78
EG # 1 (check)	Philippines	1.13	-	76	77

^aInternational Institute of Tropical Agriculture.